

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DERY****FIRST NAME: GREGORY****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 7%

The author used the following software: (MS Word – Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In research, there are three kinds of data sources which are primary, secondary, and tertiary. The knowledge of these categories can help a researcher do good research.

State the purpose of the tertiary data sources to the researcher.

- Tertiary sources help the researcher to get a broader overview of the research being done.¹**
- Tertiary sources provide the researcher with evidence to develop and justify an answer.
- Tertiary sources assist the researcher to engage in plagiarism without being caught.
- Tertiary sources help the researcher to learn from other researchers.

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 37.

2. Good research should have an engaging argument that is not negative. When is a research argument said to be negative?

- A research argument is said to be negative when the sole goal is to intimidate and win.²**
- A negative research argument is systematic and engaging.
- A research argument is negative when the researcher knows the audience will be skeptical about the argument.
- A research argument is said to be negative when other researchers disagree with the author.

3. In research writing, there are at least four reasons why authors need to cite their sources.

Which of the following is a reason why authors cite their sources?

- Authors cite sources to show they are the first to write in that area of knowledge.
- Authors cite to show humility and to acknowledge that they are the best writers.
- Authors cite sources to reassure their readers about the accuracy of their facts.³**
- Authors cite sources so that their readers understand their specific project but cannot link it to other research in that field.

4. Turabian recommends that researchers model their spelling on American usage and be consistent but makes an exception. What is the exception?

² Ibid., 56.

³ Ibid., 139.

- The exception is when the researchers model their spelling on Canadian usage.
 - When the researchers model their spelling on British usage.
 - The exception is when the researchers intend to combine several usages.
 - The exception is when, in quotations, the researchers follow the original spelling strictly.**⁴
5. In dissertation research, the student must prepare two to four documents: a dissertation concept paper, a dissertation prospectus, a dissertation, and a dissertation manuscript. While two of these documents are only prepared to enhance the research, the other two must be prepared by the student. List the two documents that the student must prepare.
- The dissertation prospectus and the dissertation manuscript.
 - The dissertation and the dissertation prospectus.**⁵
 - The dissertation and the dissertation manuscript.
 - The dissertation manuscript and the dissertation concept paper.
6. In the organization of a dissertation, one of the first tasks for the doctoral student is to develop a schema for their dissertation, which is divided into schema specialization and schema generalization. Which of the following best explains the schema generalization?
- Schema generalization is where one concept is broken into parts.

⁴ Ibid., 302.

⁵ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

- Schema generalization is the clear definition of the topic of the dissertation.
- Schema generalization is where concrete ideas are integrated into more abstract concepts.⁶**
- Shema generalization is the general outline of the dissertation.

7. In a dissertation, which Chapter is usually the Methodology Chapter?

- Chapter Four of the dissertation.
- Chapter Ten of the dissertation.
- Chapter One of the dissertation.
- Chapter Three of the dissertation.⁷**

8. There are general rules applicable to all academic writing, but there are specific rules for specific areas of study. For legal studies, the Bluebook writing rules are the specific applicable rules. Per the Bluebook rules, state the two forms that a citation may appear.

- Citation sentences or citation clauses.⁸**
- Citation clauses or citation paragraphs.
- Citation paragraphs and citation sentences.
- None of the above.

⁶ Ibid., 16.

⁷ Ibid., 34.

⁸ Mary Miles Prince, ed., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19. ed. (Cambridge, Mass: Harvard Law Review Association, 2013), 53.

9. Per Rule 12 of the Bluebook, which deals with how to cite statutes, when should a writer cite session laws?

- When the official code is unavailable or insufficient.
- When the unofficial code is insufficient or unavailable.
- None of the above.
- Both of the above.**⁹

10. Rule 15 of the Bluebook governs how books, treaties, reports, white papers, dictionaries, encyclopedias, and all other nonperiodic materials are cited. Per the Bluebook rules, mention the main elements in citing these sources.

- Author, editor, or translator, title, page or section or paragraph, edition, publisher, and date of publication.**¹⁰
- Author, editor, and date author completed school.
- Author, title, edition, publisher, and date author completed school.
- Editor, edition, and date of publication, which is optional.

⁹ Ibid., 16.

¹⁰ Ibid., 138.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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